

Analysing Spatial Distribution of Linguistic Variables in Geocoded Tweets from Croatia, Bosnia, Montenegro and Serbia

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The emerging Tweet* toolkit

TweetCat

- Uses the Search API to find users tweeting in the desired language
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TweetPub

- <https://github.com/clarinsi/tweetpub>